

" MHTFR - FOLIC ACID - METHIONINE "

How I came to discover the genetic pathology that was killing me, in 1993,
since no one understood what was happening.

MTHFR - C677T - A1298C

LUIGI BARONE

ABSTRACT

The narration of this particularly intertwined case represents a precious possibility, of study and proof, based on a true story, widely documented, which began in 1980 and ended in 2005, avoiding death.

Precisely in those years, an important research was underway, a human genome project in the acronym HGP (Human Genome Project), started in the United States in 1990 and concluded in 2000/03, in fact the two alleles C677T - A1298C emerged between 1995 and 1998.

Researching, studying, understanding and documenting for the first time, the existence of an underlying world hidden in chaos, was not easy. A world made of complex mathematical schemes and systems, difficult to understand, but I will try to give simple examples by analogies. For example, complex mathematical systems, fractal schemes can be considered. Reading complex mathematical systems allowed me to use the previous knowledge I had on such predictive schemes. The knowledge in the field of natural numbers, conquered with sacrifice, helped me, being alone, abandoned by all, dying.

I clung to the only hope, the art of knowing complex mathematical systems that I called TDC Code Theory©. It allowed me to understand, getting to the root of the problem, hidden in the chaos of events, creating clarity, to explain every related detail, through the fashion of numbers, the codes, the elements that move everything, creating unthinkable accesses, to be able to see beyond.

**"Discovering the hidden meaning of numbers,
we will discover the hidden meaning of reality"**

In fact, this thesis of mine, over time has become a reality, following the numbers, "the codes for Life", leading me to undertake further paths of studies, specializations, professional insights, in order to be of help to others, in an attempt to avoid others, the same suffering and gravity, caused to me by the metabolic problem described here, unknown to many even today, hidden in the chaos difficult to read and interpret in the usual ways, **"since the medical art, lacks by its nature of mathematical-based scientific protocols"***, unlike

Nature. *(Cassazione sent. n.301/2001, sez. I, dep. il 25 January 2005)

The study of the time, published here, leads to a very precise point, documenting a priori, the perfect synchronicity, with what is happening in the world today.

The evident clarity, the simple logic, show that the MTHFR genetic mutation (C677T – A1298C) is a complex system of metabolic ramifications, direct and indirect, towards multiple pathologies of the twentieth century, links that are unlikely to be understood.

What is indisputable, both physiologically and genetically, is to have before us complex cascade metabolic processes, non-functioning enzymatic activations, in all its conditions (Homozygous – Heterozygous) that undermine individual survival, to various percentages of enzymatic functioning, during the transformation of nutrients, determining a precarious life, due to the difficult quantitative balance of utilization of the laboriously transformed nutrients, to provide, in the moment of need, the elements necessary for survival or repair, in the difficult homeostatic balance.

Ultimately, the process of balance and support for life starts from nutrition, as well as from the introduction and breathing, also aggravated by toxic elements (metals) extracted from the body, difficult to eradicate, when our transformation, like our purification is constitutionally compromised by metabolic genetic pathways.

This redundant process, between energy consumption, recharge of deficit energies, toxicity absorbed of various kinds by the environment and by non-natural chemicals, moreover hidden without our knowledge, blocks everything, so chemistry is not tolerated.

These mutant subjects of the aforementioned alleles, are perpetually at risk of life, crimating them slowly or quickly depending on the stimulus or action carried out. For example: the introduction of drugs that prey on substances such as folate, precariously transformable, subtract energy from the body which, going into reserve, cannot cure or repair an additional need, which the body requires from any organ or system.

As well as in serious cases of inoculation of vaccines, which lead to the production of antibodies, in a mutant person (MTHFR) who cannot methylate normally and cannot produce antibodies, leading to the impairment of vital systems, to adverse reactions, for depreciated energy deficiencies, by the designed systemic action, activated by inoculation or by the introduction of substances not tolerated due to lack of adequately transformed protein energy; Methionine, Homocysteine and vice versa, creating a block of methionine or blockage of folate, for lack of ready-to-use active folate and other related substances, B6, B12, Glutathione, Vitamin C, D, E, in natural form the only one tolerated etc. This is how adverse actions happen, with many drugs that prey on folate, or other types of micro/macro/trace element nutrients.

For example: buying a drug to help us solve a problem, we also accept with the leaflet the adverse reactions described and therefore if a malaise happens the responsibility is ours and no one else's. What is different is if it is imposed, against our will or state of health. We all know that any substance that is not tolerated or toxic to the body, endangers one's health, one's life through a slow use of vital energies, laboriously transformed, to maintain vital functions.

The difference is in the action of the will or in the imposition, which leads to a permanent or serious damage, caused by the external accidental probability, normally called randomness, by the vice versa, caused by the imposition, against one's own will, having to also take responsibility. .

So not everyone can take drugs or other types of substances, adverse to them for constitutional genetic abnormalities inherited on a metabolic basis. The only suitable remedy for MTHFR Mutants, is the use of qualitative foods, active energy supports, **NON-SYNTHETIC**.

Study of galenic phytotherapeutic compounds <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5112548>

The functions of the metabolic system are divided into three groups:

1. **Energetic:** to meet the energy needs, macronutrient supply.
(Foods - carbohydrates, fats, proteins... etc.)
2. **Plasma :**to meet the need to rebuild other cells, mainly satisfied with proteins. (Foods – amino acid sequences... etc.)
3. **Bioregulators:**to ensure that all metabolic reactions take place correctly, with the contribution of micronutrients. (Foods–Vitamins–Minerals–Trace Elements Carbohydrates, Fats, Proteins... etc.)

Therefore the liver is a very important organ for the purification processes of different nature following the encounter with different toxins, of various kinds:

1. **Environmental:** Polluted, solvent pesticides, epithelium, etc.
2. **Metabolic:** Waste from intestinal flora, digestive and immune secretions, etc.
3. **Enzymatic:** Unwanted molecules through sweat, urine, bile, feces, etc.

The detoxification of the organism is therefore a complex physiological process that involves multiple biochemical stages and different actors, including amino acids deriving from the diet necessary for life.

For some time the fundamental role of the liver has been known, both to directly use amino acids for catabolic or biosynthetic purposes and to regulate the availability for the functions of the same amino acids or derivatives called to perform their task in the various districts.

Therefore amino acids can be divided into two broad categories:

- A) Tryptophan; Histidine; Methionine; Phenylalanine; Cysteine; Glutamic acid, Serine; Tyrosine; Arginine, taken by the liver and metabolized by it in exclusive or prevalent form for metabolization.
- B) Lysine; Glycine; Proline, capable of escaping the intake of the liver that will be metabolized later by other tissues.

5,10-methylentetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR) deficiency is a rare inherited disease characterized by defects in the metabolism of folate, homocysteine, methionine, etc. Individuals with hereditary mutations in the MTHFR gene have a greater tendency to develop diseases of various kinds. MTHFR polymorphisms have been extensively studied for correlation with diseases including cardiovascular disease, thrombosis, Alzheimer's disease, infertility, neural tube defects, cancer and psychiatric diseases, etc.

In conclusion: in the event that energies are plundered as a result of external or internal factors, chemical or toxic, it happens that the systems of survival, heartbeat, mind, breathing, movement, fail to support life.

The stressor received from one or more factors endangers survival, leading cascading blocks of entire basic systems for nutrition, reaction, repair.

The continuation of this vicious circle, made up of inflammation and circulating toxic elements (heavy metals) lead to continuous chronic processes, with the appearance of e.g. pain, inflammation, allergies, general functional impairment, arriving at the various pathologies related to the MTHFR genetic mutation, activating them, if predisposed or aggravating them if already present, chronicizing, up to enigmatic lethal events, due to their intertwining.

The main two systems that are involved by MTHFR are the Circulatory (C677T) and the Nervous (A1298C) or both, as a result of energy deficiencies plundered in cascade to metabolic processes. MTHFR Mutants, therefore, can not take any substance other than the natural one, since this must already be well positioned and combined, to avoid the hitches of amino acids and vitamins, for the constitutional slowed energy supply inherited from their parents, in various percentages depending on the alleles received, which compromise their existence and potential for enzymatic and energy production, not to be confused with the possible combinations of transmissibility in the act of procreation.

Not to be confused with the homozygous or heterozygous transmission action.

Let's read my story, how it all began, described in the first research 1993, to save my life, when no one knew anything or almost nothing about all this.

In support I report the study published in the Journal of Infectious Diseases, Volume 198, Issue 1, July 1, 2008. Genetics, adverse events after vaccination against smallpox. A well-established basis regarding the associated genetic factors and the development of adverse episodes by vaccine administration. There have been two independent studies. The repetition of local and systemic adverse events (AEs) on a genotyping for 1442 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) was evaluated. At the end of the study it was found that 3 SNPs were consistently associated with AE in both studies. The presence of a non-synonym SNP in the gene's methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR) was associated with the risk of adverse events in both studies. Genetic polymorphisms in genes expressing an enzyme previously associated with adverse reactions to a variety of pharmacological agents (MTHFR) and an immunological transcription factor (IRF1), were associated with adverse events after smallpox vaccination in the 2 independent study samples.

<https://academic.oup.com/jid/article/198/1/16/841083#90060068>

Finally, the hope should come from the natural galenic "Compound 10", in which mass spectrometry has highlighted the presence of short switchable peptides, with great potential at the functional biochemical level.

<https://doi.org/0.5281/zenodo.5112548>

Eboli li, 31 August 2021

Luigi Dr. Barone

Independent Researcher Graduated in Food Science and Human Nutrition, General Nutritional Epidemiology, Food Allergies and Intolerance, Naturopathy, Scientific Journalist specialized in: Clinical Dietetics, Eco-Environmental Toxicity, Herbal Medicine, Phytotherapy, Social Psychology, Motor Activities, Tourism

Sciences, Communication Sciences, Graphics, P.A. (C.V. updated)

INDIVIDUAL STUDY TO UNDERSTAND WHAT WAS HAPPENING TO ME

It all began with Alpha-1-Antitrypsin, this is a glycoprotein synthesized by the liver capable of an **inhibiting** action on the activity of **trypsin** and other proteolytic enzymes such as **chymotrypsin**, thrombin, elastase. In the specific case, it should be noted that the only proteolytic enzyme that is inhibited by the alteration, is that of Alpha-1-Antitrypsin, is that of **chymotrypsin**, in fact the values of Alpha 1-antitrypsin are high, this alteration has also been found in case of gastric, hepatic and pancreatic pathologies.

Currently there is a chronic gastritis, with a slight presence of HP, which alternates between negativity and positivity.

So the alteration of Alpha-1-Antitrypsin, explains the low value of chymotrypsin found in the feces, and consequently, the pathology present, chronic gastritis, which means inflammation, justifying this alteration.

Given that gastritis, in a direct and indirect way, is the basis of 90% of diseases, it can be easily cured definitively with the appropriate diet, except in cases where this pathology does not depend on an excess of Helycobacter Pyloribacteria. In the specific case, there is no excess of such a bacterium, but its alternating presence is strange.

The altered values of IgE and the low values of the lymphocyte subpopulation and its CD3, CD4, CD8 properties, can be attributed both to the presence of the bacterium Helycobacter Pylori and to the various allergies and food or chemical intolerances, found present in the specific case, as well as the presence of heavy metals of cadmium and aluminum, detected by the mineralogram. It is likely that the set of several factors, over time, have created a vicious circle, such as to determine the particular situation, difficult to manage.

Usually gastritis is due to an excess of gastric juice, which leads to reflux and an increase in the volume of the stomach, increasing acidity in the intestine. All this causes a greater absorption of the ingested substances, therefore, an increase in fat (in all parts of the body, including cellulite), which is totally opposite to the case treated. In addition, a lot of gas lying in the intestine, from here, a swollen intestine, can lead to back pain, constipation, and the substances present in colon necrosis, **with related fouling**, present in the descending colon as evidenced in the MRI report.

Comparing the subjective data we have an opposite situation, with regard to weight gain, produced by the increase in acidity. In a nutshell there is an inverse situation: a severe organic deterioration, with the presence of scale in the colon of probable alimentary nature (calcium = milk).

Returning again to the alteration of **Alpha-1-Antitrypsin**, the other element to consider is tryptase. The various proteins of wheat, barley, rye etc. contain IgE towards albumin proteins, agglukinin, a glycoprotein (purified concanaline A) that is a trypsin inhibitor.

Given that in the specific case there are also high values of Amylase, a digestive enzyme capable of splitting oligosaccharides and polysaccharides into smaller compounds (disaccharides) and that serum amylase is mainly produced by the pancreas and parotid glands, this justifies intolerance to the grass family, even if there is currently no presence of allergies to gluten or diseases related to it, despite the predisposition highlighted in the HLA1 and HLA2 examination of the LOCUS DQ = DQ2 and DQ7(3) Celiac disease.

An increase in amylase can also occur in the presence of inflammatory lesions, justifying the alteration of Alpha 1 Antitrypsin, and therefore also in that of Chronic Gastritis, the deficiency of folic acid, which as a result of poor digestion leads us to a bad absorption, even of B12, limiting nutrition, **but here perhaps the case goes much further, probably of a genetic nature.**

The low presence of potassium and the desire for salt, perhaps due to the vicious circle created, justifies the low presence of Aldosterone, which is the main mineralocorticoid hormone produced by the adrenal gland.

Considering that there are no other abnormalities of another type or causes, given that stress, **the state of the immune system, inflammations, infections, allergies depend on the simultaneous presence of three essential vitamins, B6 + Pantothenic Acid + Folic Acid**, since the **deficiency of one of the three vitamins blocks the production of antibodies** and slows down the activity of the adrenal glands, it comes that any action is in vain if one of these vitamins is missing.

Currently it has been widely established that there is a constant deficiency of folic acid, and that **no doctor** has ever recommended or prescribed a **folate therapy (active)**.

This deficiency would justify the various relationships between allergies, stress, inflammation, etc., moved by a single element, the absence of folic acid or the excessive presence of methionine cumulated with various foods, difficult to convert due to the limping enzyme 10%-50%.

The case is more complicated when the most imputed foods are Eggs, Soy, Milk, Fish, (as well as Yeast, Graminaceae, Liliaceae, Additives, Preservatives, etc.) that contain choline, where its main constituent is Lecithin, a phospholipid.

This leads us to premature birth, so not having been fed with breast milk, only later, but with the cow's milk, which caused at an early age, to a **deadly phase by intoxication, aggravated by antibiotics due to a persistent fever, it consequently compromised the gastric-immune-endocrine system.**

At this **point, acetylcholine** could come into play with the nervous system, considering that this situation has persisted for decades. Poor digestion certainly leads to poor absorption and a reduction in the introduction of food.

At this point everything can or could also be aggravated by a genetic deficiency, total or partial, of some enzyme.

We cannot understand the cause precisely, but an alternative nutrition could certainly

lead to improvements, which in turn would shed light on who first moves the reins of the case, having also arrived with my mathematical method to require specific analyzes, choices in the complex genetic heritage examined, leading me to the amino acid homocysteine, found subsequently altered, and folic acid with low levels for decades, never considered by doctors of all levels.

All the research carried out led me to the idea of having to consult and encourage pharmaceutical companies to produce a revolutionary drug also for other diseases, containing a simple combination and **union of folic acid in MTHFR form, Vitamin B12, VITAMIN B6, or the three vitamins that are used for the conversion of methionine into cysteine**, and vice versa, to prevent it from becoming homocysteine.

This alteration also explains the multiple allergic reaction and food intolerance, given that methionine is in all foods in varying amounts as a sulfur-containing amino acid. Thus, the impossibility of producing glutathione, due to lack of active substances and conversion deficit, becoming UMFA substances, suitable for producing adequate antibody defenses, leading the lymphocyte subpopulation and its ratios to have few sentinels to defend people, not being able to produce them because of the MTHFR enzyme functioning only at 10% - 20%, creating life danger due to energy deficiency, to keep the body alive. From this it follows that every non-natural and active foreign element, (chemical) introduced for any reason, leads to sudden aggravations even of immediate death, for serious metabolic dysfunctions due to lack of constitutional genetic enzymatic transformation, inherited from the parents (congenital defect with autosomal recessive transmission) and other consequences related to all the remaining systems and systems.

Just in those years, the first specific laboratory tests for such **evaluations** began to come out: genetics, **MTHFR, confirmed my diagnosis**, built over time laboriously, and not before adequate sweats and specialization diplomas, saving my life by activating the therapy studied, finding it in natural form, since **other folic acid formulations were FASULLE**, had no effect on **me, MUTANT MTHFR double Heterozygous C677T and A1298C**, all tested and tested directly at various dosages and times, to understand and try not to die.

In **conclusion**, it is because of that missing genetic piece for the conversion of nutrients, that enzyme with expression reduced to several %, which has revolutionized my existence, complicating nutrition in support of life, a serious metabolic process, which thanks to knowledge and passion was born the Natural Mathematical Medicine I designed, avoiding death, bringing with me a permanent damage to life. I promised myself, to study to save others like me, staying away from chemistry, from toxicities of all kinds, finding in creation and in nature the only true way, mother nature, which provides us with life, air, water, food, etc.

Eboli 11 September 2006 at 5.23

Luigi Barone

Copyright: © 2006/2021 by the authors. Luigi Barone Eboli – Italy – Pagineonline.org
This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions
of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

8650 N. 22nd Ave. • Phoenix, AZ 85021 • (602) 995-1581

SESSO: M

ETA': 34

DATA: 4/06/93

NR. LABORATORIO: 133798

NR. CLIENTE: 94589

NOME DEL PAZIENTE: **Luigi Barone**

Testing By Accutrace Labs, CLIA# 03D0641886 8650 N. 22nd Ave. Phoenix, AZ 85021

LIVELLO MINERALI TISSUTALI

136	20	85	34	11.9	8.5	0.68	68	0.40	0.60	54.4
128	19	80	32	11.2	8.0	0.64	64	0.38	0.57	51.2
120	18	75	30	10.5	7.5	0.60	60	0.36	0.54	48.0
112	17	70	28	9.8	7.0	0.56	56	0.34	0.52	44.8
104	16	65	26	9.1	6.5	0.52	52	0.32	0.48	41.6
96	15	60	24	8.4	6.0	0.48	48	0.30	0.45	38.4
88	14	55	22	7.7	5.5	0.44	44	0.28	0.42	35.2
80	12	50	20	7.0	5.0	0.40	40	0.24	0.36	32.0
72	11	45	18	6.3	4.5	0.36	36	0.22	0.33	28.8
64	10	40	16	5.6	4.0	0.32	32	0.20	0.30	25.6
56	9	35	14	4.9	3.5	0.28	28	0.18	0.27	22.4
48	8	30	12	4.2	3.0	0.24	24	0.16	0.24	19.2
40	7	25	10	3.5	2.5	0.20	20	0.14	0.21	16.0
32	6	20	8	2.8	2.0	0.16	16	0.10	0.15	12.8
24	5	15	6	2.1	1.5	0.12	12	0.08	0.12	9.6
16	4	10	4	1.4	1.0	0.08	8	0.06	0.09	6.4
8	3	5	2	0.7	0.5	0.04	4	0.04	0.06	3.2
8	2	5	2	0.7	0.5	0.04	4	0.02	0.03	3.2
8	1	5	2	0.7	0.5	0.04	4	0.02	0.03	3.2
46.00	5.00	21.00	12.00	1.50	.90	.04	19.00	.02	.04	14.00
CALCIO	MAGNESIO	SODIO	POTASSIO	FERRO	RAME	MANGANESE	ZINCO	CRONIO	SELENIO	FOSFORO
(Ca)	(Mg)	(Na)	(K)	(Fe)	(Cu)	(Mn)	(Zn)	(Cr)	(Se)	(P)

TEST PRECEDENTE

METALLI TOSSICI

ELEMENTI TRACCIA

2.5	0.5	0.10	1.75	3.0	0.40	8.8	0.44	0.8	0.8
2.0	0.4	0.08	1.40	2.7	0.35	7.7	0.33	0.7	0.7
1.5	0.3	0.06	1.05	2.1	0.30	6.6	0.22	0.6	0.6
1.0	0.2	0.04	0.70	1.8	0.25	5.5	0.11	0.5	0.5
0.5	0.1	0.02	0.35	1.5	0.20	4.4	0.04	0.4	0.4
0.5	0.1	0.02	0.35	1.2	0.15	3.3	0.03	0.3	0.3
0.5	0.1	0.02	0.35	0.9	0.10	2.2	0.02	0.2	0.2
0.5	0.1	0.02	0.35	0.6	0.05	1.1	0.01	0.1	0.1
0.5	0.1	0.02	0.35	0.6	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.0
.10	.04	.06	N/A	2.10	.03	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PIOMBO	MERCURIO	CADMIO	ARSENICO	ALLUMINIO	NICKEL	COBALTO	MOLOBDENO	LITIO	BORO
(Pb)	(Hg)	(Cd)	(As)	(Al)	(Ni)	(Co)	(Mo)	(Li)	(B)

TEST PRECEDENTE

OSSIDATORE MISTO

IPEROSSIDATORE

IPOSSIDATORE

N/A - NON DISPONIBILE RILEVATO IN Mo% COPYRIGHT 1981 ANALYTICAL RESEARCH LABS, INC.

Varianti del gene 5, 10-metilentetraidrofolato reduttasi e anomalie congenite: una revisione enorme FREE

Lorenzo D. Botto , Quanhe Yang

American Journal of Epidemiology , Volume 151, Numero 9, 1 maggio 2000, pagine 862-877, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.aje.a010290>

Pubblicato: 01 maggio 2000 **Storia dell'articolo** ▼

 Condividere ▼

Astratto

L'enzima 5, 10-metilentetraidrofolato reduttasi (MTHFR) è coinvolto nel metabolismo dei folati. Il gene MTHFR è localizzato sul cromosoma 1 (1p36.3) e sono stati descritti due alleli comuni, l'allele C677T (termolabile) e l'allele A1298C. La frequenza della popolazione dell'omozigosi C677T varia dall'1% o meno tra i neri dell'Africa e degli Stati Uniti al 20% o più tra gli italiani e gli ispanici statunitensi. L'omozigosi per C677T nei neonati è associata a un rischio moderatamente aumentato di spina bifida (odds ratio = 1,8; intervallo di confidenza al 95%: 1,4, 2,2). Anche l'omozigosi materna C677T sembra essere un fattore di rischio moderato (odds ratio = 2,0; intervallo di confidenza al 95%: 1,5, 2,8). Il Anche l'allele A1298C combinato con l'allele C677T potrebbe essere associato ad un aumento del rischio di spina bifida. Alcuni dati suggeriscono che il rischio di spina bifida associato all'omozigosi C677T può dipendere dallo stato nutrizionale (es. livelli di folati nel sangue, assunzione di vitamine) o dal genotipo di altri geni correlati ai folati (es. cistationina-β-sintasi e metionina sintasi). reduttasi). Gli studi sull'allele C677T in relazione a schisi orali, sindrome di Down e sindrome anticonvulsivante fetale hanno prodotto risultati contrastanti o non sono stati ancora replicati. *Am J Epidemiol* 2000; 151: 862-77.

anomalie A1298C C677T epidemiologia genetica 5, 10-metilentetraidrofolato reduttasi difetti del tubo neurale disrafismo spinale

Sezione problema: EPIDEMIOLOGIA DEL GENOMA UMANO ENORMI RECENSIONI

Acido folico Livelli bassi d'acido folico sono stati trovati in pazienti con la malattia di Crohn. Quest'insufficienza è responsabile per lo sviluppo della neuropatia periferica e risponde bene con supplementi di acido folico.

Alterazioni dei parametri di laboratorio indotte da farmaci

Farmaci che alterano l'acido folico (nel siero)

(a cura di Giuseppina Fava e Alessandra Russo, Dipartimento Sperimentale e Clinico di Medicina e Farmacologia, Università degli Studi di Messina).

Principio attivo (Nome Commerciale)	Aumento	Riduzione
Acido acetilsalicilico (<i>Acesal, Algopiridina, Alkaseltzer, Alsogil, Antinevralgico Knapp, Antireumina, Ascriptin, Aspegic, Aspidol, Aspiglicina, Aspirina, Aspirinetta, Aspro 500, Bufferin, Cardioaspirin, Cardirene, Cemirit, Contralgen, Doloflex, Drin, Flectadol, Geyfritz, Kilios, Migpriv, Migraprim, Murri A/dolorifico, Neocibalgina, Neocoricidin, Neonevral, Neonisidina, Neouniplus, Upsalgina, Verdal, Viamal, Vivin C</i>)		↓
Acido mefenamico (<i>Lysalgo</i>)		↓
Alcool		↓
Ampicillina (<i>Ampilisa, Ampilux, Ampiplus, Amplital, Amplium, Amplizer, Bethacil, Diamplicil, Ibimicyl, Loricin, Pentrexy, Unasyn</i>)		↓
Antagonisti dell'acido folico		↓
Antiacidi		↓
Bicarbonato		↓
Carbamazepina (<i>Carbamazepina Teva, Tegretol, Tegretol CR</i>)		↓
Cloramfenicolo (<i>Antibiopital, Betabiopital, Chemicetina, Chloromycetin, Cloramfen, Colbiocin, Cortifluoral, Cortison chemicetina, Cosmiciclina, Dexoline, Eubetal antibiotico, Fluorobiopital, Iruxol, Ismicetina Ini, Mycetin, Sificetina, Vasofen, Vitamfenicolo, Vitceaf, Xantervit antib</i>)		↓
Colchicina (<i>Colchicina Lirca</i>)		↓
Colestiramina (<i>Questran</i>)		↓
Contraccettivi orali		↓
Eritromicina (<i>Eritrocina, Eritrocist, Eritromicina Galderma, Eryacne, Erythroclin, Ilosone, Lauromicina, Rubrociclina, Stellamicina, Zelig, Ziheryt</i>)		↓
Estrogeni		↓
Etinilestradiolo acetato (<i>Diane, Egogyn, Eugynon, Evonor, Fedra, Ginoden, Harmpnet, Mercilon, Microgynon, Milvane, Minulet, Novogyn, Ovranel, Planum, Practil, Securgin, Trigynon, Triminulet, Trinordiol</i>)		↓
Fenformina (<i>Bidiabe, Gliben, Gliformin, Suguan</i>)		↓
Fenitoina (<i>Aurantin, Dintoina, Dintoinale, Gamibetal complex, Metinal Idantoina</i>)		↓
Fenobarbital (<i>Comizial, Dintoinale, Gamibetal complex, Gardenale, Luminale, Luminalette, Metinal idantoina, Neurobiol C.M.</i>)		↓
H2-antagonisti		↓
Isoniazide (<i>Etanicozid B6, Isoniazide, Miazide B6, Nicizina, Nicozid, Rifater, Rifinah</i>)		↓
Metformina (<i>BI Euglicon M, Glibomet, Gliconorm, Glucomide, Glucophage, Glucosulfa, Metbay, Metforal, Metiguanide, Pleiamide, Suguan M</i>)		↓
Metotrexato (<i>Brimexate, Methotrexate, Metotrexato DBL, Metotrexato Teva</i>)		↓
Neomicina (<i>Abiostil, Anauran, Antibiopital, Bimixin, Biodelta, Ciatrene, Desalfa, Desamix, Doricum, Ecoval, Enterostop, Etabiocortilen, Halciderm Combi, Idracemi, Idrocet, Idroneomicil, Kataval, Localyn, Locorten, Menaderm, Mixotone, Neffuan, Neoaudiocort, Neocortofen, Neomedrol, Nevacort, Orobicin, Otosporin, Rinojet Valeas, Solprene, Streptosil Neomicina, Trofodermin, Vasosterone</i>)		↓
Nitrofurantoina (<i>Furadantin, Furedan, Furul, Macrodantin, Neofuradantin</i>)		↓
Penicillina		↓
Pentamidina (<i>Pentacarinat, Pneumopent</i>)		↓
Pirimetamina (<i>Metakelfin</i>)		↓
Primidone (<i>Mysoline</i>)		↓
Sulfasalazina (<i>Salazopyrin, Salisulf</i>)		↓
Tetraciclina		↓
Triamterene (<i>Fluss</i>)		↓
Trimetopim (<i>Abacin, Bacterial forte, Bactrim, Chemitrim, Eusaprim, Kelfiprim, Lidaprim</i>)		↓